

Kinetics and mechanism of ruthenium(III) chloride catalyzed oxidation of formic acid by peroxomonosulphuric acid in acid aqueous medium – An appraisal of hydride ion transfer

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Abstract : The kinetics of ruthenium(III) chloride catalyzed oxidation of formic acid by peroxomonosulphuric acid (PMS) have been studied in acid aqueous medium. The stoichiometry corresponds to the reaction as represented by the eq. (1),

The rate of reaction is independent of the per-acid concentration. However, formic acid exhibits a complex dependence. The kinetic rate law is represented by the eq. (2),

$$-\frac{d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_h[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}][\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + K_h[\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]} \quad (2)$$

A plausible reaction mechanism has been suggested.

Keywords : Kinetics, mechanism, ruthenium(III), catalysis, oxidation, formic acid, peroxomonosulphate.

Introduction

Peroxodisulphate oxidations of various organic compounds ascribe to the formation of free radicals. In case of oxidation of oxalate and formate by peroxodisulphate, a CO_2^- radical is reportedly^{1,2} formed. When peroxodisulphate reacts with formate under identical experimental conditions as that of the oxalate, the former reaction is much faster than the latter and corresponds to the stoichiometry of one mole of persulphate for one mole of formic acid. The results of oxidation of formate by peroxodisulphate also are at variance and pH dependence is not well defined.

Peroxomonosulphuric acid (H_2SO_5) can be considered to be a compound of substituted hydrogen peroxide in which one of the hydrogens is replaced by an oxyanion of sulphur. This is indeed a more powerful oxidizing agent than its parent analogue peroxodisulphate³. A mixture of $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, H_2SO_5 and H_2O_2 employed by Hart⁴ in radiolytic decomposition of formic acid also suggests that peroxomonosulphuric acid is more reactive than peroxodisulphuric acid.

These were certain observations that prompted us to

undertake metal-ion catalyzed oxidation of formic acid by peroxomonosulphuric acid with the following aspects to probe further apart from understanding the mode of reactivity of peroxomonosulphate in solution.

First formic acid is the simplest organic acid which can provide better information about the catalytic pattern of ruthenium(III) chloride in its oxidation with peroxomonosulphate. Secondly, since peroxomonosulphate is reduced to sulphate ions and formic acid is oxidized to carbondioxide, the mode of interaction of the catalyst can be delineated without any interferences from either of the oxidation products. Thirdly the radiolytic studies^{3,4} of peroxomonosulphate have been reported with the formation of OH and $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ free radicals, further probing of the title reaction is worth attempting to understand whether or not these radicals have any role to play in thermal reactions. Also, persulphate reactions are normally chain reactions⁵ whether or not such a chain reaction chemistry is exhibited in peroxomonosulphate reactions.

Experimental

Peroxomonosulphate, a triple salt (2KHSO_5 , KHSO_4 ,

K_2SO_4 (Aldrich) was employed as received. However, analysis of the sample iodometrically³ or ceremetrically shows it to be ~96% pure. The presence of H_2O_2 was negated as the tests with permanganate indicated its absence. Neta *et al.*³ have reported that H_2O_2 even of concentration $< 10^{-6}$ mol dm^{-3} was not detected. Also, their attempts to purify this salt failed to get it in pure form. It has been found that the impurity of ~4% accounts for the presence of $KHSO_4$ or K_2SO_4 or both. The solution of peroxomonosulphate was thus prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of the salt in doubly distilled water. The solution is quite stable if kept at refrigerated temperature (~5 °C) in bottles painted black from the outside. Nevertheless, solutions of peracid were prepared afresh as and when required for kinetic studies.

The details regarding preparation of other reagents have already been reported elsewhere. Doubly distilled water was employed both for preparation of the reagents as well as the reaction mixtures for kinetic analysis, second distillation was from alkaline potassium permanganate solution in an all glass apparatus.

Kinetics of the reaction were carried out by conducting reactions in a thermostated water-bath maintained at ± 0.1 °C unless stated otherwise. The reaction ingredients except peroxomonosulphate were taken in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks. An aliquot of temperature pre-equilibrated solution of desired concentration was taken out and then added into the reaction mixture. The mixture was shaken vigorously and the time of initiation of the reaction was recorded when half of the contents from the pipette were released. The kinetics were monitored iodometrically by assaying remaining peroxomonosulphate. An aliquot (5 cm^3) was withdrawn periodically and then discharged into ~10% iodide solution. The liberated iodine was titrated against thiosulphate solution employing starch as an indicator without any interference. The results in triplicate were reproducible to within $\pm 6\%$.

Initial rates (k_i , mol dm^{-3} s^{-1}) were computed employing plane-mirror method⁶. Pseudo-first order plots were also made wherever reaction conditions permitted.

Stoichiometry : The stoichiometry of the reaction was carried out by undertaking reactions with an excess of peroxomonosulphate (heretofore written as PMS) over that of formic acid in a thermostated water bath at ± 0.1 °C for *ca.* 10 h. The remaining peroxomonosulphate after the reaction was determined iodometrically³.

These results correspond to the stoichiometry as represented by the eq. (1).

The formation of carbon dioxide was tested qualitatively. However, similar stoichiometry has also been reported earlier⁷.

Results

The dependence of peroxomonosulphate on the initial rate, heretofore referred to as only rate or $-d[PMS]/dt$, instead of, initial rate was examined at three different but fixed concentrations of formic acid, viz. 5.0×10^{-2} , 7.5×10^{-2} and 10×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} respectively. The rate is independent of peroxomonosulphate concentrations exhibiting zero order with respect to peracid. The concentration of PMS vs time plots are a distinct straight lines. The zero order rate constants calculated from these plots were independent of the initial concentrations of peroxomonosulphate (Table 1).

The concentration of formic acid was varied in the range $(2.0-10.0) \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients and also at 20, 25 and 30 °C respectively. The zero order rate constants (k' , mol dm^{-3} s^{-1}) were calculated and the plots of k' against the concentrations of formic acid exhibited linear increase at lower concentrations and then tended to attain a limiting rate at higher concentrations of the formic acid.

The concentration of ruthenium(III) chloride was varied in the range $(1.0-5.0) \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} at fixed concentrations of other reaction components viz. $[PMS] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[HCO_2H] = 0.05$ mol dm^{-3} and $[H_2SO_4] = 0.01$ mol dm^{-3} . The plot of rate constants against the concentration of the catalyst yielded a straight line passing through the origin indicating first order with respect to ruthenium(III) (Table 1). The concentration of sodium perchlorate was varied from 0.2 to 1.0 mol dm^{-3} keeping constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. $[PMS] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Ru^{III}] = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} and pH 4.48. The rate remains unchanged with the variation of sodium perchlorate.

pH dependence : The pH of the reaction mixture was varied from 3.46 to 4.74 employing acetate buffer at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. $[PMS]$

Table 1. Initial rates (k_i) and second order rate constants in the reaction of formic acid and peroxomonophosphoric acid catalyzed by ruthenium(III) chloride

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. 25 °C

10^3 [PMS] (mol dm ⁻³)	10^2 [HCO ₂ H] (mol dm ⁻³)	10^3 [Ru ^{III}] (mol dm ⁻³)	10^7 (k_i) (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	10^2 k (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
1.0 (2.0)	5.0	1.0 (1.0)	16.6 (17.4)	16.6 (17.4)
1.5 (2.0)	5.0	1.0 (1.5)	16.3 (22.9)	16.3 (15.3)
2.0 (2.0)	5.0	1.0 (2.0)	16.6 (34.0)	16.6 (17.0)
2.5 (2.0)	5.0	1.0 (2.5)	16.6 (41.2)	16.6 (16.5)
3.0 (2.0)	5.0	1.0 (3.0)	16.6 (47.2)	16.6 (15.7)
3.5 (2.0)	5.0	1.0 (3.5)	16.1 (56.2)	16.1 (16.1)
4.0 (2.0)	5.0	1.0 (4.0)	15.8 (67.2)	15.8 (16.8)
4.5 (2.0)	5.0	1.0 (4.5)	16.6 (77.5)	16.6 (17.2)
5.0 (2.0)	5.0	1.0 (5.0)	15.8 (86.3)	15.8 (17.3)
1.0	7.5	1.0	22.5	22.5
1.5	7.5	1.0	21.3	21.3
2.0	7.5	1.0	23.0	23.0
2.5	7.5	1.0	22.5	22.5
3.0	7.5	1.0	22.9	22.9
3.5	7.5	1.0	22.2	22.3
4.0	7.5	1.0	22.9	22.9
4.5	7.5	1.0	21.6	21.6
5.0	7.5	1.0	22.9	22.9
1.0 (2.0)	10.0	1.0 (1.0)	27.1 (28.0)	27.1 (28.0)
1.5 (2.0)	10.0	1.0 (1.5)	27.0 (41.0)	27.0 (27.4)
2.0 (2.0)	10.0	1.0 (2.0)	27.5 (57.1)	27.5 (28.5)
2.5 (2.0)	10.0	1.0 (2.5)	27.1 (70.5)	27.1 (28.0)
3.0 (2.0)	10.0	1.0 (3.0)	27.1 (85.5)	27.1 (28.5)
3.5 (2.0)	10.0	1.0 (3.5)	27.0 (101.2)	27.0 (28.5)
4.0 (2.0)	10.0	1.0 (4.0)	27.1 (112.5)	27.1 (28.1)
4.5 (2.0)	10.0	1.0 (4.5)	27.7 (127.5)	27.7 (28.7)
5.0 (2.0)	10.0	1.0 (5.0)	28.0 (141.0)	28.0 (28.2)

= $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HCO}_2\text{H}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 22, 25 and 28 °C respectively and $I = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The rate increases with increasing pH.

The effect of salts such as NaNO_3 , NaCl and LiCl was also studied in the concentration range (0.2–1.0 mol dm⁻³) at fixed concentrations of other reaction components viz. $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HCO}_2\text{H}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and pH 4.48. The rate remains unaffected by the addition of these salts. The effect of benzene and *t*-butyl alcohol respectively was studied and the rate remained unchanged. It is, therefore, clear that neither OH nor $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ radical participates in the reaction.

The reaction was also followed at 22, 25 and 28 °C

respectively keeping constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HCO}_2\text{H}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and pH 4.48. The energy and entropy of activation to be $(50 \pm 4) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $(-65 \pm 8) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively were calculated in a conventional manner.

Discussion

A general mechanism for the oxidation of most of the nucleophiles by peroxomonosulphate and other peroxides involves the heterolytic cleavage of the peroxide ($-\text{O}-\text{O}-$) bond in the rate controlling steps. Such a step is supported by the comparison of activation parameters reported for the oxidation of wide range of nucleophiles

including halides, sulphide and nitrite by inorganic and organic peroxides⁸⁻¹¹. Peroxomonosulphate ion is a mono-substituted derivative of H₂O₂ (HOOSO₃⁻) and is more reactive kinetically than H₂O₂ even though it is only slightly more powerful oxidant ($E^{\circ} = +1.82$ V) than H₂O₂ ($E^{\circ} = +1.776$ V)^{12,14}. HSO₅⁻ is more stable than H₂O₂ as far as spontaneous decomposition in water is concerned. The acid pH employed in the title reaction^{15,16} is far less than pK₂, the possibility of peracid existing in the form of SO₅²⁻ is therefore ruled out. Thus peroxomonosulphate predominantly exists as HSO₅⁻ and it is the only reactive form of the peracid.

The dissociation constant of formic acid is reported³ to be pK = 3.8. If one takes into account the characteristics of the pH dependence on the formate-peracid reaction, the rate increases from pH 3.46 to 4.74 and then shows maximum rate between pH 5-7. Such an observed pH dependence characteristics are analogous to those reported earlier in the oxidation of formate by Hart⁵, Flynn and House¹⁷, Halpern and Taylor¹⁸ in the oxidation of formate by many inorganic oxidant in perchloric acid solution. Halpern *et al.*¹⁸ remark in their final conclusions that the pH dependence owes more to the differences in reactivity of HCO₂H and HCO₂⁻.

Ru^{III}Cl₃ exists in various forms in dil. HCl and it is exceedingly difficult to decide which species of the catalyst is involved in the rate controlling step. Connick and Fine^{19,20} on the basis of spectroscopic analysis showed the existence of the species Ru^{III}Cl₃ as [RuCl₅(H₂O)], [RuCl₄(H₂O)₃], [RuCl₂(H₂O)₄]⁺, [RuCl(H₂O)₅]²⁻ and [Ru(H₂O)₆]³⁺. This later species is assumed to be the ruthenium(III) species and the hydrogen ion dependence can be correlated to it considering its hydrolysed species [Ru(H₂O)₆]²⁺ to be the reactive form. The hydrolysed form of ruthenium(III) is preferred to HCO₂⁻ species to account for catalysis exhibited by the former. Thus the mechanism for the reaction can be proposed by taking into account the following steps (2) to (5).

Such a mechanism leads to the rate law (6) or (7),

$$-\frac{d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = \frac{kK K_h [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + K K_h [\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]} \quad (6)$$

where [Ru^{III}]_T and [HCO₂H] are the gross analytical concentration of ruthenium(III) and free equilibrium concentration of formic acid respectively.

or

$$k' = \frac{kK K_h [\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + K K_h [\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]} \quad (7)$$

where k' is an observed first order rate constant.

The rate law (7) can be further re-arranged to eq. (8),

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{[\text{H}^+] + K_h}{kK K_h [\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (8)$$

A plot of 1/ k' versus 1/[HCO₂H] was made from eq. (8) that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 1). Let I_1 be the intercept which is equal to 1/ k from eq. (8), k was calculated to be $(3.6 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-1}$, $(5.9 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-1}$ and $(8.3 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 22, 25 and 28 °C respectively.

Another plot was further made between 1/ k' and [H⁺], which also yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept. which intercept (I_2) and slope (S_2) from this plot were calculated as were given by eqs. (9) and (10) respectively,

$$I_2 = \frac{1}{k} + \frac{1}{kK[\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]} \quad (9)$$

and

$$S_2 = \frac{1}{kK K_h [\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]} \quad (10)$$

Thus the value of ' K ' was evaluated by substituting the values of k , K_h and constant concentration of [HCO₂H] in eq. (10). Similarly ' K_h ' was calculated from eq. (11) which was obtained by combining eqs. (8), (9) and (10).

$$K_h = \frac{[\text{H}^+](I_2 - I_1)[\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]}{S_2 - \{(I_2 - I_1)[\text{HCO}_2\text{H}]\}} \quad (11)$$

These values of k , K_h and K are collected in Table 2.

The fact that one-equivalent oxidation of formic acid or formate ion should be favoured only with very potential oxidants of one equivalent type. Since the formation of free radicals is negated, it appears that the complex between Ru^{III} and formic acid undergoes oxidative rupturing via hydride ion abstraction from the substrate⁴ rather

Fig. 1. A plot of $(k')^{-1}$ versus $[HCOOH]^{-1}$ is the reaction of peroxomonosulphate and formic acid. $[PMS] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[Ru^{III}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[H_2SO_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (O), 20°; (Δ) 25° and (\square) 30 °C.

Table 2. Rate constant, hydrolytic constant and complex formation constant in ruthenium(III) catalysed peroxomonosulphate-formic acid reaction

	22 °C	25 °C	28 °C
$k \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	$(3.6 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-1}$	$(5.9 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-1}$	$(8.3 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-1}$
K_h	$(3.6 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-4}$	$(7.0 \pm 0.8) \times 10^{-4}$	$(10 \pm 1) \times 10^{-4}$
$K \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$	(133 ± 10)	(550 ± 40)	(750 ± 60)

than forming one-equivalent peroxomonosulphate free radical. This is also in line of other peroxomonosulphate reactions where the free radical of the former has not been indicated in its redox reactions.

Although the activational requirements favour H atom transfer over hydride ion transfer as two electron transfer step has considerable advantages of energy over higher energy one electron transfer formation of an intermediate radical ion²¹.

The heterolytic breaking of the (-O-O-) peroxide bond in the rate limiting step has been suggested for the oxidation of most of the nucleophiles by peroxides including peroxomonosulphuric acid and are based on the activation parameters calculated in the oxidation of wide range of nucleophiles such as halides, sulphides and nitrites⁹⁻¹⁷.

If hydride ion abstraction by ruthenium(III) as has been

suggested to be the selective mode of redox reaction, the following Scheme 1 can be envisaged to account for the experimental observations.

Scheme 1

Thus the catalyst redox cycle ($\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{I}}$)^{22,23} or ($\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}$)^{24,25} is operative and the hydride ion transfer appears to be a reasonable mode of electron transfer from the substrate to the oxidant. Since the rate does not depend upon the concentration of the oxidant, the possibility of operation of $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}$ redox cycle of the catalyst is ruled out.

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